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FTM and PDR Based Dynamic Mapping for Indoor Localization Enhanced by Wi-Fi Aware

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Abstract—This paper addresses the challenge of device localization within a Wi-Fi network. It introduces a novel localization technique, using a pre-constructed map with predefined positions around an Access Point (AP). The Wi-Fi client devices (STAs), are positioned on the map utilizing the capabilities of the Fine Time Measurement (FTM) protocol (IEEE 802.11mc), and tracked using the Pedestrian Dead Reckoning (PDR) method, which leverages the device’s Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS). It also harnesses the capabilities of Neighbor Awareness Networking (NAN) technology, to discover the distances between Wi-Fi Aware certified devices. This method requires no additional equipment or prior setup, since one AP is sufficient to determine the STA’s position. The findings suggest that this approach provides a scalable and efficient solution for IoT applications.

Index Terms—Internet of Things (IoT), Indoor Positioning, Fine Time Measurement (FTM), Neighbor Awareness Networking (NAN), Wi-Fi Aware, Pedestrian Dead Reckoning (PDR), Micro-Electro-Mechanical Systems (MEMS)

I. INTRODUCTION

A key challenge in the Internet of Things (IoT) is achieving positioning accuracy, especially indoors, where signals from Global Positioning System (GPS) are weak. This paper proposes a relatively simple technique that utilizes a pre-constructed map with predefined positions, evenly distributed half a meter apart, around the router on concentric circles. It utilizes the Fine Time Measurement (FTM) protocol (IEEE 802.11mc) [1], to progressively build a fingerprint around the router. By tracking devices as they move through space using the Pedestrian Dead Reckoning (PDR) method, the Time of Flight (TOF) reading for each position is recorded and marked in green for Line of Sight (LOS) conditions, and in orange or

red for Non-Line of Sight (NLOS) situations. Progressively, obstacles are identified and marked on the map, forming a fingerprint of the surrounding area.

Unlike prior work, this method requires no dedicated infrastructure, such as multiple Access Points (APs) or Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) beacons, by using Neighbor Awareness Networking (NAN)-enabled device collaboration and a single AP. Wi-Fi Aware allows devices to communicate without a traditional Wi-Fi network or internet, making it ideal for IoT applications. Integrating NAN for peer-to-peer FTM ranging and dynamic map refinement using crowd-sourced PDR data is a key innovation over existing Received Signal Strength Indicator (RSSI) and FTM hybrid approaches. Wi-Fi Aware and NAN technologies for indoor positioning are an emerging field with limited but promising research.

II. RELATED WORK

To achieve indoor positioning as reliably and accurately as the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS), researchers have utilized technologies such as Wi-Fi, BLE beacons, radio frequency identification (RFID), ultrasonic technology, and ultra-wideband (UWB), often in combination with other techniques. Wi-Fi-based ranging approaches are generally classified into two main categories: RSSI based and ToF-based [2]. Numerous studies have utilized RSSI, examining how radio signal attenuation occurs during propagation. However, recent research has increasingly incorporated the FTM protocol, part of the IEEE 802.11-2016 standard, which has gained significant attention in the scientific community since its release. One of the earliest studies, conducted by Intel [3], explored

the effectiveness of Kalman and Bayesian filters. Two years later, in research [4] conducted an in-depth assessment of FTM's precision and accuracy, testing in both outdoor and indoor environments across the 2.4GHz and 5GHz bands. Their findings indicate that FTM, as opposed to RSSI, can offer reliable meter-level ranging in open spaces.

Research on PDR methods such as [5], propose positioning techniques that use sensor fusion of Wi-Fi and IMU data through an Extended Kalman Filter. These techniques estimate user heading by using accelerometers, gyroscopes, and magnetometers, while addressing magnetic field distortions through a real-time direction detection algorithm. Reference [6] introduces a federated filter approach to merge the Round-Trip Time (RTT) measurements with sensor data. One approach, detailed in [7], combines RTT and PDR models geometrically, solving the position using optimization methods rather than filtering.

Although previous studies have explored the combination of FTM and PDR for tracking, no existing solution integrates it with (i) NAN-based device-to-device ranging, (ii) radial map initialization with environment calibration, and (iii) crowd-sourced obstacle detection through collaborative PDR tracking.

III. RANGING WITH WI-FI

Wi-Fi-based positioning methods are widely used for indoor positioning, owing to the widespread presence of Wi-Fi APs in numerous locations. In Wi-Fi technology, at least one of the following key indicators is required for range estimation: time or signal strength. This involves measuring either the time a packet takes to travel from one device to another using FTM, or assessing the RSSI values at the client device. These measurements are fundamental for providing an estimation of the device's distance [8].

A. Ranging with FTM

The FTM protocol, as specified in the 2016 revision of the 802.11 standard (802.11-mc), has gained significant recognition for its ability to accurately measure ranging, and it has been extensively covered and used in other research endeavors. This protocol introduces a novel approach, to estimate the RTT of the signal journey between the transmitter and the receiver, independent of clock synchronization [1].

The distance of a Wi-Fi client device from the AP, can be determined using the FTM protocol by measuring the RTT. The TOF is half the RTT, calculated based on the speed of light. Environmental delays are identified from initial LOS measurements and incorporated into the expected TOF values (Table I).

$$\text{ToF} = \frac{\text{Distance}}{c} + \tau \quad (1)$$

where (τ) is the difference between the anticipated TOF and the actual measurement of TOF using a test device, containing delays caused by the environment and hardware.

TABLE I
TOF VALUES IN LOS FOR ALL POSITIONS

R (m)	Positions	Interval (m)	TOF (ns)	TOF + τ (ns)
0.5	6	0.479426	1.667	1.97
1.0	13	0.494808	3.333	3.47
1.5	19	0.497688	5.000	5.05
2.0	25	0.498699	6.667	6.78
2.5	31	0.499167	8.333	8.54
3.0	38	0.499421	10.000	10.31
3.5	44	0.499575	11.667	11.90
4.0	50	0.499675	13.333	13.56
4.5	57	0.499743	15.000	15.31
5.0	63	0.499792	16.667	16.98
5.5	69	0.499828	18.333	18.66
6.0	75	0.499855	20.000	20.33
6.5	82	0.499877	21.667	22.05
7.0	88	0.499894	23.333	23.74
7.5	94	0.499907	25.000	25.36
8.0	101	0.499919	26.667	27.10
8.5	107	0.499928	28.333	28.77
9.0	113	0.499936	30.000	30.42
9.5	119	0.499942	31.667	32.11
10.0	126	0.499948	33.333	33.80
10.5	132	0.499953	35.000	35.48
11.0	138	0.499957	36.667	37.14
11.5	145	0.499961	38.333	38.81
12.0	151	0.499964	40.000	40.56
12.5	157	0.499967	41.667	42.20
13.0	163	0.499969	43.333	43.92
13.5	170	0.499971	45.000	45.58
14.0	176	0.499973	46.667	47.22
14.5	182	0.499975	48.333	48.90
15.0	188	0.499977	50.000	50.58

In NLOS situations, the direct path is blocked by obstacles and the wireless signal interacts with these obstructions, leading to signal attenuation, reflections, diffraction, and scattering [9]. As a result, TOF increases significantly in NLOS scenarios, leading to an overestimation of distance when using the above equation in reverse. The measurements presented in the last column of table I, are averages of 1000 FTM readings per distance. By subtracting the theoretical TOF from the measured TOF, the combined delay (τ) can be utilized in practice, to improve the accuracy of real-time distance estimations. For the Samsung S24 Ultra smartphone and Google Nest Pro router used in our experiments, was found to be approximately 0.387 ns.

B. Ranging with NAN

Wi-Fi Aware is a certification program by the Wi-Fi Alliance that allows devices to discover and communicate directly using NAN technology, without requiring traditional Wi-Fi or internet. Devices establish peer-to-peer connections via applications, using a publish/subscribe model. They broadcast their presence and listen for other devices during designated discovery windows.

A device that publishes a service allows others to subscribe to it, initiating a communication channel. The NAN Discovery Engine manages service queries and responses, with applications handling the communication. NAN also supports ranging, allowing devices to measure distance using the FTM protocol. The initiator sends FTM requests, and the responder

Fig. 1. NAN Architecture

replies, enabling the initiator to calculate the distance based on signal travel time. NAN supports concurrent operation, allowing devices to be part of a NAN network while using other Wi-Fi networks, which is useful for proximity-based applications like location services [10].

In NAN, devices take dynamic roles to maintain network stability and synchronization. The NAN Master device transmits synchronization and discovery beacons to keep cluster timing, while Non-Master devices follow this timing for service discovery and data exchange. The highest-ranking device, the Anchor Master, acts as the main synchronization point. Periodic NAN synchronization beacons help devices align internal clocks, managed by the Master or Anchor Master. The NAN Medium Access Control (MAC) layer manages synchronization and service discovery frames, while the Physical Layer (PHY) layer handles data transmission. NAN APIs allow applications to publish, subscribe, and create data paths, with the data engine and scheduler ensuring reliable communication and efficient medium use [10].

Wi-Fi Aware security relies on cryptographic mechanisms to protect communication. NAN Data Pairwise Security Associations (ND-TKSA) secure unicast communication using AES-based encryption, while Group Transient Keys (GTK) and Integrity Group Transient Keys (IGTK) protect multicast data and management frames. Secure pairing is achieved through NAN Certificate Suite Public Key Two-Way Diffie-Hellman (NCS-PK-2WDH) and NAN Certificate Suite Symmetric Key (NCS-SK). Privacy is maintained via HMAC-SHA-256-derived Service Identifiers (SIDs), while Beacon Integrity Group Transient Key Security Association (BIGTKSA) prevents unauthorized beacon modifications. Despite strong encryption, vulnerabilities remain, such as unencrypted synchronization beacons susceptible to spoofing and the lack of Denial-of-Service (DoS) mitigation. Future work should enhance beacon encryption, spoofing detection, and DoS prevention mechanisms [10].

The technique operates at the application layer, reducing firmware dependencies by leveraging OS APIs, such as Android's FTM and NAN frameworks. Devices must comply with IEEE 802.11 standards and be Wi-Fi Aware-certified, to support NAN functionalities like Synchronization Beacons and Ranging. FTM ranging, PDR step detection, and NAN communication are executed via OS libraries for real-time map updates. While deployment is simplified through app-level updates, underlying NAN-compliant firmware remains essential for device discovery. This approach ensures compatibility with consumer devices and existing Wi-Fi Aware ecosystems, enabling scalable adoption in smart environments.

Overall, these components create a robust framework for direct, local communication, enhancing the capabilities of Wi-Fi devices to support a wide range of proximity-based applications and services [11].

IV. PROPOSED METHOD

The technique uses a predefined TOF map (Eq.1) with 50 cm resolution, refined as STAs move around the AP. PDR tracks their paths in LOS/NLOS identifying obstacles, similar to the transit method in astronomy, where dips in starlight reveal planets [12]. This process constructs a fingerprint of the environment, which is further calibrated via trilateration using nearby NAN-enabled STAs.

A. Map Initialization

On the map in Fig. 2, there are 2922 possible positions, evenly distributed every 0.5 meter around the router, which is at the center. Each circle has a possible position every about 0.5 meter on its circumference. The chosen distance is 50 cm, which approximates the space an average person occupies while standing. The initialization algorithm computes positions using Equations 2-4, where $D = 0.5\text{m}$. Environmental calibration involves an initial LOS measurement at a known distance to determine τ , which is stored as a persistent offset for subsequent TOF adjustments.

The circumference of circles with radii ranging from 0.5 to 15 meters is first calculated. Dividing C by the desired distance D (0.5 in this case) between points:

$$P = \frac{C}{D} \quad (2)$$

and then rounding the result, it yields an integer number of possible positions P' which will be placed on every circle, with approximately D distance between them. For better area coverage, the number of points can be increased, by decreasing the distance between them.

For the circle to be divided into equal parts, the angle θ subtended by each chord at the center of the circle must be:

$$\theta = \frac{2\pi}{P} \quad (3)$$

The chord length can be calculated based on this angle, ensuring that the circumference is divided into approximately equal segments.

Fig. 2. Final map around the AP. Positions in green correspond to TOF values expected in LOS conditions, including delays caused by the environment and hardware. Positions in orange indicate TOF values greater than the expected LOS values, indicating obstacles in between. Red positions show even higher TOF values, after considering the delays observed in orange, suggesting the presence of more obstacles. Black positions were never visited, indicating potential obstacles.

The following formula derives from the geometry of the circle and finds the chord length for a given radius with P' points on its circumference. The result is the distance between positions on each inner circle, shown in table I :

$$\text{chord_length} = 2 \times \text{radius} \times \sin\left(\frac{\theta}{2}\right) \quad (4)$$

The expected TOF values are given by equation 1, for each position at distances from 0.5 up to 15 meters away from the router. For instance, at a distance of 6 meters away from the AP, at 75 possible positions spaced 0.499855 cm apart, the expected TOF is 20 ns in LOS situation plus τ , as seen in table I. If this reading is obtained during an FTM packet exchange, it means that τ is zero, and its possible position is one of these predefined 75 positions. The information kept for every point is the ID, the coordinates, the angle around the circle, distance from the router, whether it is an obstacle or not, the expected TOF in LOS, the observed TOF and the nearby points at a predefined distance, which are the user's next possible positions. Initially, every point is considered an obstacle until it is visited and measured.

B. PDR movement monitoring

PDR involves following a pedestrian's position, by continuously updating the position estimate, based on the user's detected steps, acceleration and heading direction. Step detection identifies individual steps from the accelerometer data, typically using a peak detection algorithm on the vertical acceleration component. Step length estimation can be achieved through linear or nonlinear models, that relate the peak acceleration during a step to the step length, often calibrated for individual walking patterns. Heading estimation leverages the

magnetometer and gyroscope data, where the magnetometer provides a compass heading and the gyroscope measures the rate of rotation to update the heading direction [13].

In Figure 2, the map around the AP is shown with several possible positions. Devices have already connected and moved around the space. Their movements were monitored using the PDR method with IMU sensors, while continuously exchanging FTM packets with the AP and marking positions based on TOF readings.

Once a device is within range and its distance is determined, its position is estimated along the negative x-axis, allowing the system to compute its next possible locations and update the map. These positions will be at a maximum radius distance W around the current position, extending in all directions, given by:

$$W = \sqrt{\max^2 + \min^2} + \sqrt{\max^2 - \min^2} + (\max - \min) \quad (5)$$

Values $\max = 0.499977\text{m}$ and $\min = 0.479426\text{m}$ denote the maximum/minimum inter-position distances from Table I. The search radius $W = 0.855\text{m}$ ensures coverage of all plausible next positions. It is derived using three geometric components of these distances: the square root of the sum of the squares of the maximum and minimum values, the square root of the difference of the squares of these values, and the direct difference between them. All points within W radius will be considered as a next possible position, ensuring it is the first point in every direction, without extending beyond it.

Using FTM or PDR alone for ranging, can lead to incorrect position estimations, due to delays caused even by the human body acting as an obstacle [14]. However, sensors such as the gyroscope, accelerometer, and magnetometer, can determine if the user is moving, in which direction and at what speed, and most importantly the distance he has covered. FTM readings will confirm and adjust user's position, while the map is continuously updated.

To mitigate carrying mode and body occlusion effects, we implement body-shadowing compensation and IMU error correction. When NLOS is detected, indicated by a time-of-flight (TOF) measurement exceeding $1.2 \times TOF_{expected}$, the step length is reduced by 30% based on empirical observations in [14]. Additionally, IMU error correction is performed using a Kalman filter that fuses accelerometer and gyroscope data. The filter is tuned for smartphone-grade MEMS sensors as described in [6], with process noise set to $Q = 0.1I_{3 \times 3}$ and measurement noise set to $R = 0.5I_{3 \times 3}$.

In this positioning system, the user's movement is tracked on a 2D plane with concentric circles and points spaced at intervals of D , along each circumference. At any given position, the user's next location will fall within a minimum radius of D and a maximum radius of W . The heading direction is determined from gyroscope and magnetometer data, using the cascaded complementary filter approach described in [15]. Step detection and acceleration data are obtained using a peak detection algorithm, and step length is calculated through a linear model, as shown in [16]. With this information, the user's location can be matched to a position on the map based

Fig. 3. NAN Network

on the Euclidean distance travelled. The possible positions around the current location lie within a maximum radius W in all directions, given by:

$$\mathbf{p}_{k,i} = \mathbf{p}_k + W \begin{bmatrix} \cos(\phi_i) \\ \sin(\phi_i) \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

for $i = 1, 2, \dots, N$, where N is the number of possible positions calculated at intervals of $\Delta\phi = \frac{2\pi}{N}$.

C. Wi-Fi Aware and Trilateration / Multilateration

In Figure 3, Wi-Fi Aware-certified STAs continuously exchange FTM packets with the AP, to determine their distance from it. They also calculate the distance between each other using FTM within the NAN technology, and all this information is shared with the Anchor Master device for position estimation. In NAN networks, a Wi-Fi Aware device can be part of more than one NAN cluster, but there can be only one Anchor Master device in each cluster, synchronizing cluster activities and maintaining timing coordination among devices.

Using trilateration or multilateration with at least three NAN STAs and the AP, their positions can be accurately determined and adjusted on the map. These devices play a crucial role in constructing the map and adjusting its orientation, but all

Fig. 4. Positioning Process Flow

devices contribute to creating a fingerprint of the surrounding environment by recording the TOF at every predefined position they visit, identifying obstacles within the AP's range. By leveraging the combined capabilities of FTM, PDR, and NAN technologies on a preconstructed map with optimized position allocation, every device can be accurately placed within the AP's vicinity.

Trilateration and multilateration are essential techniques for Wi-Fi indoor positioning, determining a device's coordinates by measuring distances to multiple known anchor points.

In trilateration, the 2D position (x, y) is estimated using distances r_1 , r_2 , and r_3 from three non-collinear anchors at (x_1, y_1) , (x_2, y_2) , and (x_3, y_3) . The system is defined by:

$$r_i = \sqrt{(x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2}, \quad \text{for } i = 1, 2, 3 \quad (7)$$

Squaring and subtracting these equations linearizes the problem into a solvable system, as demonstrated in [17].

NAN ranging utilizes the IEEE 802.11mc FTM protocol, typically performing 10 bursts per measurement. Device-to-device distances are shared via NAN Service Discovery Messages (SDMs), which include the identifiers of both the initiating and responding devices, along with the measured RTT [10]. For $N \geq 3$ anchors, position estimation uses the Levenberg-Marquardt nonlinear least-squares optimization:

$$\min_{x,y} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\sqrt{(x - x_i)^2 + (y - y_i)^2} - d_i \right)^2 \quad (8)$$

where d_i are measured distances.

This optimizer balances speed and robustness in noisy environments. Multilateration generalizes this by using three or more anchors, creating an over-determined system. Weighted

least squares minimizes residual errors, improving robustness against measurement noise [17].

Figure 4 illustrates the system’s process, from the moment a device enters range to the finalization of its position. Distance is first measured for any FTM-enabled device, followed by movement monitoring. If three or more Wi-Fi Aware devices are present, they exchange distances via NAN service discovery, enabling trilateration and multilateration for refined positioning. Once a device’s position is identified, the system updates its status and computes possible next positions. Upon step detection, data from the accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer estimate step length and movement direction. The new position is then confirmed via FTM, dynamically updating the map. This continuous process maintains an accurate, real-time map of the environment and obstacles, relying on precise FTM measurements and sensor-based movement tracking.

V. TESTING AND SIMULATION APPROACH

The feasibility of the proposed system was evaluated, by testing its core components under controlled conditions using a Samsung S24 Ultra smartphone and a Google Nest Pro router. FTM ranging was validated by measuring distances at predefined positions around the AP, arranged along concentric circles. Accuracy and consistency in FTM readings, confirmed reliable distance estimation based on predefined TOF values, adjusted by τ to account for hardware and environmental delays. Wi-Fi Aware devices were also tested using NAN to measure inter-device distances, demonstrating their ability to exchange ranging data and support collaborative localization. Integration of PDR data was validated through smartphone applications utilizing MEMS-based IMU sensors (accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer).

VI. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

Compared to existing works, our research offers a more holistic and adaptive indoor localization system by integrating FTM, PDR, and Wi-Fi Aware into a unified framework. Unlike research [16], which relies solely on RTT measurements and Kalman filtering without incorporating real-time map updates, our system dynamically adapts to environmental changes through collaborative mapping. Similarly, research [3] propose a Bayesian fusion of FTM and map data, but their dependence on static, pre-constructed maps limits flexibility and scalability in evolving indoor environments. The authors in [5], improve accuracy through Wi-Fi and IMU fusion using Gaussian Process Regression and step estimation, yet their approach lacks peer-to-peer device interaction and remains reliant on centralized infrastructure. Despite its advantages, our method has limitations: it requires *Wi-Fi Aware*-certified devices for full functionality, and its effectiveness depends on the accuracy of the PDR component, which can be affected by sensor noise and user movement variability. The distinguishing feature of our approach, is its ability to identify and locate obstacles by adjusting the map according to deviations from anticipated TOF readings in LOS, creating obstacle shadows. A real-world

implementation of the proposed system is planned as part of our future research efforts.

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